
ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH AND INCOME INEQUALITY

MISSION

DATASET SOURCE

- World Bank Open Data
- Links : (1) <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD>
(2) <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG>
- Databases used were: (1) GDP Per Capita (Current US \$) and (2) GDP Per Capita Growth (Annual %)
- Databases include data of the world for the period 1960-2017
- Databases were last updated on 10/18/18

RAW DATA

Data Source	World Development Indicators													
Last Updated Date	10/18/18													
Country Name	Country Code	Indicator Name	Indicator Code	1960	1961	1962	1963	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970
Aruba	ABW	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Afghanistan	AFG	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	59.7773265	59.8781528	58.4928738	78.782758	82.2084439	101.290471	137.899362	161.322	129.506654	129.798541	157.187422
Angola	AGO	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Albania	ALB	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Andorra	AND	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											3238.55685
Arab World	ARB	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD									222.619525	238.835301	256.341059
United Arab Emirates	ARE	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Argentina	ARG	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD			1148.57996	845.077184	1166.3174	1272.0105	1266.34499	1057.75566	1136.51783	1324.08293	1317.48776
Armenia	ARM	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
American Samoa	ASM	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Antigua and Barbuda	ATG	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Australia	AUS	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	1807.34978	1874.30477	1851.42482	1963.63908	2127.5669	2277.06668	2339.86194	2575.62008	2719.4298	2986.21889	3299.0373
Austria	AUT	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	935.460427	1031.815	1087.83424	1167.00053	1269.41258	1374.53214	1486.96861	1569.66718	1677.67353	1825.38613	2058.76908
Azerbaijan	AZE	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Burundi	BDI	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	70.3490786	71.4872777	73.7817649	78.9002836	86.6031946	51.6573647	52.476723	55.1316867	55.2434042	56.0788814	70.2431271
Belgium	BEL	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	1273.69166	1350.19767	1438.52323	1535.02373	1701.84628	1835.59477	1957.62608	2086.63601	2222.36151	2458.08182	2780.69619
Benin	BEN	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	93.022509	95.5721547	94.464535	99.8591139	104.339768	110.132794	112.940836	111.951602	116.895066	116.025094	114.556596
Burkina Faso	BFA	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	1342193.05	71.5581801	76.5206114	78.3720719	80.4727667	81.7251155	82.5456369	84.3631649	84.7330493	86.5202111	81.4998987
Bangladesh	BGD	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	88.6912106	97.1427302	99.5767137	101.260491	99.5038643	105.78917	111.658639	121.662093	121.528898	133.575437	138.247965
Bulgaria	BGR	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Bahrain	BHR	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Bahamas, The	BHS	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	1550.32431	1651.47548	1752.97029	1867.11299	1994.54492	2144.83097	2322.94385	2556.8353	2804.70513	3215.48667	3179.27627
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BIH	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Belarus	BLR	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Belize	BLZ	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	304.917107	316.403606	327.126867	336.941466	351.161126	377.594305	406.097967	420.431888	386.953237	396.654306	435.690469
Bermuda	BMU	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	1902.40212	1961.53817	2020.38597	2020.26525	2199.72701	2282.21655	2630.85047	2982.7497	2830.18868	3053.7037	3387.27273
Bolivia	BOL	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	152.461846	162.695705	174.493386	184.275535	203.601149	223.27833	239.374916	255.847966	210.18989	218.555801	225.748299
Brazil	BRA	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD	210.02747	204.929302	260.225266	291.950589	261.331083	260.964693	315.277382	346.8801	374.083262	403.065252	444.026268
Barbados	BRB	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											
Brunei Darussalam	BRN	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD						1113.40245	1237.07924	1235.8921	1363.45304	1303.73941	1381.97217
Bhutan	BTN	GDP per capita (current US\$)	NY.GDP.PCAP.CD											

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Country Name	Country Code	Indicator Name	Indicator Code	1960	1961	1962	1963	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970
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Arab World	ARB	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
United Arab Emirates	ARE	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Argentina	ARG	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		3.747272986	-2.41045374	-6.77162564	8.464397201	8.934658915	-2.08931231	1.736490265	3.339587227	8.077918766	1.4678
Armenia	ARM	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
American Samoa	ASM	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Antigua and Barbuda	ATG	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Australia	AUS	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		0.466561385	-1.14587827	4.196692121	4.8998858	3.926693581	0.071393841	4.968988552	3.25806872	4.826983749	5.0813
Austria	AUT	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		4.960717183	2.021469667	3.471466159	5.419336014	2.810012786	4.904479004	2.241009758	3.931241829	5.909495926	5.9504
Azerbaijan	AZE	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Burundi	BDI	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		-15.3730014	7.027770432	2.149477734	4.122311144	1.703465938	2.129435451	10.96016311	-2.76951669	-3.65362056	19.083
Belgium	BEL	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		4.630257134	4.794034518	3.574353541	5.949139356	2.624444661	2.461462453	3.291575742	3.785044364	6.328283647	5.487
Benin	BEN	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		1.708894548	-4.85516414	3.084114416	4.872974956	3.438229481	1.652640175	-0.88559102	1.748705061	0.745684799	-0.064
Burkina Faso	BFA	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		2.656018055	4.722128332	-2.59342458	0.857187825	2.24102302	-1.02109047	7.058359024	1.344304081	0.288794717	-1.599
Bangladesh	BGD	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		3.079001648	2.482799237	-3.30257692	7.679938429	-1.49637194	-0.70361743	-5.08136836	6.00666389	-1.7126581	2.9725
Bulgaria	BGR	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Bahrain	BHR	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Bahamas, The	BHS	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		5.302375571	5.001573965	5.099103738	5.240886599	5.414207372	4.368226936	5.114623215	4.308452632	5.252022489	-8.494
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BIH	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Belarus	BLR	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Belize	BLZ	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		1.969342153	2.004937561	2.043422663	2.040458056	1.914698841	1.677936409	1.799021034	4.250586943	2.286170371	2.3020
Bermuda	BMU	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		2.149274725	2.003969957	-1.26075472	8.383374233	2.250778443	12.34545455	11.0966736	0.178748759	1.520936744	4.3793
Bolivia	BOL	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		0.145004135	3.55448463	4.373050887	2.760511205	3.55607945	4.392363424	4.77789416	-13.9349447	1.004796804	-2.530
Brazil	BRA	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG		7.095696419	2.163610897	-2.04302305	0.534549621	0.178577915	1.31141482	2.115373308	8.516388961	6.927923817	6.0409
Barbados	BRB	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Brunei Darussalam	BRN	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											
Bhutan	BTN	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG											

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WORLD'S INCOME PER PERSON (US \$) VS ECONOMIC GROWTH (%)

- No particular relationship between world's income per person and economic growth
- Increase in world's income per person from 2010 to 2014
- Decrease in world's economic growth from 2010 to 2012
- No fixed pattern of increase or decrease in income per person and economic growth

WORLD'S MEAN INCOME PER PERSON (US \$)

Mean Income Per Person (US \$), 2010-2016

Top 3:

- Norway : 90.83K
- Switzerland: 82.88K
- Australia: 59.86K

WORLD'S ECONOMIC GROWTH (%)

Top 3:

- China : 7.56%
- Mongolia: 6.51%
- Myanmar: 6.49%

Note: Annual percentage growth rate of GDP per capita is based on constant local currency.

TOP 10 RICHEST COUNTRIES

Based on 2016 Income Per Person

TOP 10 RICHEST COUNTRIES INCOME PER PERSON TREND

Luxembourg's income per person was above US \$100,000

TOP 10 RICHEST COUNTRIES ECONOMIC GROWTH TREND

Top Ten Rich Countries Economic Growth, 2010 - 2016

Ireland's economic growth reached a peak 24.376534% in 2015

INCOME PER PERSON G-20 NATIONS

Top 3: Australia, United States, Canada

ECONOMIC GROWTH G-20 NATIONS

Economic Growth of G20 Nations, 2010-2016

China tops the list in overall economic growth between 2010-2016

AUSTRALIA VS CHINA

- Income Per Person(US \$) of Australia was way higher than that of China.
- Economic Growth(%) of China was way higher than that of Australia.

FASTEST GROWING COUNTRY - INCOME PER PERSON – G20 NATIONS

Top 3: United States, Korea Republic, China
The difference of 2016 and 2010 income per person of G20 Nations was taken into account

FASTEST GROWING COUNTRY - ECONOMIC GROWTH - G20 NATIONS

United Kingdom and Australia were the only two G20 Nations with positive economic growth percent when the difference between 2016 & 2010 economic growth was taken into account

SAARC COUNTRIES INCOME PER PERSON

Maldives was way above in the spectrum followed by Sri Lanka and Bhutan

SAARC COUNTRIES ECONOMIC GROWTH

Pakistan is the only SAARC nation which has consistently increased in annual economic growth rate. However, the growth rate percentage is fairly small.

MALDIVES INCOME PER PERSON & ECONOMIC GROWTH, 2010-2016

Maldives income per person fairly increased throughout 2010-2016. However, the economic growth rates were negatives during 2012 and 2015

CONCLUSIONS

- No particular relationship/ No fixed pattern of increase or decrease between world's income per person and economic growth.
- Top 3 in terms of world's mean income per person(US \$): (1) Norway (2) Switzerland (3)Australia.
- Top 3 in terms of world's in terms of world's economic growth(%) : (1) China (2) Mongolia (3) Myanmar. It is also important to note that annual percentage growth rate of GDP per capita is based on constant local currency.
- Based on 2016 dataset, Luxembourg, Switzerland, Norway, Ireland, Iceland, Qatar, United States, Singapore, Denmark and Sweden were the top 10 richest countries. It was also found out that Luxembourg's income per person was well above \$100,000 between 2010-2016.
- It was amazing to see Ireland's economic growth of 24.376534% in 2015.
- Top 3 among G20 Nations in terms of Income Per Person were Australia, United States, Canada
- China topped the list of G20 Nations in overall economic growth between 2010-2016.
- Income Per Person(US \$) of Australia was way higher than that of China. However, Economic Growth(%) of China was way higher than that of Australia. This clearly demonstrates economic growth and income inequality.
- Top 3 were United States, Korea Republic and China when the difference of 2016 and 2010 income per person of G20 Nations was taken into account. Also, United Kingdom and Australia only had positive economic growth percent when the difference of 2016 and 2010 economic growth of G20 nations was implemented.
- Out of all the SAARC countries, Maldives had the highest income per person. However, Pakistan was the only SAARC nation which had consistently increased in annual economic growth rate.

LEARNING PROCESSES

- Python is a fun language
- “A picture speaks a thousand words” - Matplotlib is a popular Python library that helps a person to visualize the data clearly and understand it thoroughly. Plotly serves the same function empowered by online collaborative data analysis and graphing tool.
- Build something, anything to keep learning Python
- With more experience in Python, I can definitely improve my code

REFERENCES

- Choropleth Maps. (n.d.). Retrieved November 10, 2018, from <https://plot.ly/python/choropleth-maps/>
- GDP per capita (current US\$). (n.d.). Retrieved November 10, 2018, from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD>
- GDP per capita growth (annual %). (n.d.). Retrieved November 10, 2018, from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.KD.ZG>

